

Scrum

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Definition of Scrum

Scrum (n): A framework within which people can address complex adaptive problems, while productively and creatively delivering products of the highest possible value. Scrum is:

- Lightweight
- Simple to understand
- Difficult to master

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The life cycle of the scrum method is composed of several Sprints described in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Cycle de vie de la méthode Scrum

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Bibliography

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Dr ian mitchell

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